

Strain Analysis in Discontinuous Fiber-Reinforced Metals Using the Moiré Grid Method

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ABSTRACT

Moiré strain analysis was applied to discontinuous fiber-reinforced composite metals under tension. The effects of matrix stress-strain characteristics, discontinuous fiber arrangements and fiber volume fraction on the strain distribution in composites were investigated. Stainless-steel fiber-reinforced Pb-5Sn alloy, tungsten fiber-reinforced aluminum and tungsten fiber-reinforced nickel were fabricated as models. Strains in the matrix were concentrated around the fiber end. The higher the matrix work-hardening or strength, the lower was the concentration of these strains. In stainless steel / Pb-5Sn the work-hardening of which is little, the stress distribution in discontinuous fiber almost agreed with the Kelly-Tyson equation or the Piggott equation. The strain concentration in the matrix resulting from the fiber overlapping model of $l_o/l_f=0.5$ (l_o :overlap fiber length, l_f :full fiber length) was the lowest. And these strain concentrations decreased on increasing fiber volume fraction. On the other hand, critical fiber length was found to decrease on increasing fiber volume fraction.

INTRODUCTION

Discontinuities in fibers is of great interest regarding whisker-reinforced metals, unidirectional eutectic alloys and even for continuous fiber-reinforced metals, because continuous fibers may break during fabrication or at low stress levels when flaws exist. Thus the micromechanics of discontinuous fiber-reinforced materials have been widely investigated both theoretically and experimentally.⁸⁾ However, the case of elastic matrix has been applied to many of them. Few studies have been concerned with plastic matrix, and in particular only a small number of investigations have been experimentally based.⁹⁾ In the case of the metal matrix composite, matrix plasticity should be considered.

The purpose of this report is to examine experimentally the strain distribution that occurs in discontinuous fiber-reinforced composite metals using two-dimensional moiré grid analysis. The advantage of this technique is that the plastic strain of real fiber-reinforced composite metals may be analysed. We examined the effects of matrix stress-strain characteristics and the interaction between neighboring fiber discontinuities and fiber volume fraction on the strain distribution of discontinuous fiber-reinforced composite metals.

The strengthening mechanics and fracture mechanics of discontinuous or continuous fiber-reinforced composite metals are discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL MODEL AND PROCEDURE

Models

Four types of models were studied in this investigation. The geometries of the models and reference coordinates are shown in figure 1.

(a) was a single short fiber model. The effects of different stress-strain characteristics of the matrix on the strain distribution of matrix and fiber were investigated using this model. Stainless steel / Pb-5Sn alloy, tungsten / aluminum and tungsten / nickel were adopted as fiber / matrix combinations. Table 1 shows their mechanical properties. The composite models were prepared by vacuum hot-pressing. The thickness of the matrix was 1 mm. The diameter and aspect ratio of fiber was $0.5\phi \times 64$. Short fiber was placed on a matrix sheet and covered with a 20 μm -thick foil of matrix metals and mica in carbon dies. Vacuum hot-pressing was then carried out.

The overlapping model of (b) was designed for the purpose of investigating the effects of various discontinuous fiber arrangements on fiber and matrix strain distributions. The amount of overlapping l_o/l_f (l_o :overlap fiber length, l_f :full fiber length) was varied from 0 to 1 for the changing of interacting discontinuity. Lateral fiber spacing was $5 d_f$ (d_f :fiber diameter).

(c) and (d) were surrounding fiber models. Central discontinuous fibers were surrounded by many continuous fibers. In model (c), the central fiber was a single short fiber with non-interacting discontinuity. In model (d), the central fiber end was set to the other central fiber end. This model represents the situation in composites where two fibers are aligned with their ends close together or where a fiber has broken. The change in lateral fiber spacing, that is, the change of fiber volume fraction, was studied. In model (d) the change in the gap between the central fiber ends was also studied. Matrix and fiber dimensions of models (b), (c), (d) were the same as for model (a). These models were made using tungsten fiber and aluminum matrix by vacuum hot-pressing. It was considered that the fiber composite was loaded parallel to the fiber under tension.

Moiré Strain Analysis

The grid used was of 40 lines/mm. It was copied onto the specimen surfaces by photosensitive preparations. A photosensitive lacquer was coated onto the specimen surfaces. The grid was placed in contact therewith and exposed to ultraviolet irradiation. The image was developed and dyed blue.

Moiré fringes were produced by Moiré camera. In this camera, the specimen grid was projected through distortion-free lenses onto the analyzer grid. Moiré fringes were recorded on film attached behind the analyzer grid. Figure 2 shows the moiré fringe pattern in W / Al around the fiber end.

Strain at the surface of the specimen was computed using moiré fringe space δ and alignment ϕ by applying the mismatch technique. Strains were given by

$$\epsilon_x = (P_x/P_o) \cos\theta_x \sec(\theta_x - \theta_y) - 1 \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon_y = (P_y/P_o) \cos\theta_y \sec(\theta_x - \theta_y) - 1 \quad (2)$$

$$\gamma_{xy} = \theta_x - \theta_y \quad (3)$$

θ_x , θ_y , P_x and P_y were calculated from the following equations.

$$\left\{ \frac{1}{P_o(1+m)} \right\}^2 = \frac{2\cos\theta_x}{P_o P_x} + \frac{1}{P_x^2} = \frac{1}{\delta x^2} \quad (4)$$

Fig.1 Fiber distribution and dimensions of models

Table 1 Values of some mechanical properties of fibers and matrices

	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Shear Modulus (GPa)	Proof Strength (MPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)
Pb-5Sn	15	5.8	10.3	35.3
Al	69	26.7	20.6	91.1
Ni	206	75.5	63.7	314
Stainless steel	186	-	-	2300
W	343	-	-	1960

Fig.2 Moiré fringes in W / Al around short fiber end

$$P_x = \delta_x \sin \phi_x \sec \theta_x \quad (5)$$

$$\left\{ \frac{1}{P_o(1+m)} \right\}^2 = \frac{2 \cos \theta_y}{P_o P_y} + \frac{1}{P_x^2} = \frac{1}{\delta_y^2} \quad (6)$$

$$P_y = \delta_y \sin \phi_y \sec \theta_y \quad (7)$$

where

ϵ_x, ϵ_y : Normal strain-with respect to the x-axis or y-axis

γ_{xy} : Shear strain

P_o : Specimen grid pitch before deformation

m : Mismatch

θ_x, θ_y : Specimen grid orientation with respect to the x-axis or y-axis after deformation

P_x, P_y : Specimen grid pitch with respect to the x-axis or y-axis after deformation

ϕ_x, ϕ_y : Moiré fringe alignment with respect to the x-axis or y-axis

δ_x, δ_y : Moiré fringe space with respect to the x-axis or y-axis

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mechanical Properties of Matrices and Micromechanics of Discontinuous Fiber-Reinforced Alloys.

In figure 3, contours for the principal strain, nondimensionalised with respect to average strain, at the surface of single short fiber models are shown. The principal strain in the matrix was concentrated at the extreme outside tip of the fiber. Especially in the case of stainless steel / Pb-5Sn, the strain concentration at this place was about 30 times as large as the average composite strain $\bar{\epsilon}_c$ at $\bar{\epsilon}_c = 4.1 \times 10^{-3}$. Even at this small $\bar{\epsilon}_c$, almost all areas of the matrix yielded. However, in the case of W / Ni, the principal strain concentration was about 2.8 times $\bar{\epsilon}_c$ and far smaller than that of stainless steel / Pb-5Sn. This strain concentration decreased in the order of stainless steel / Pb-5Sn, W / Al and W / Ni, with increasing matrix elasticity, work-hardening and strength.

The same tendency was observed in interfacial shear strain along the fiber. Figure 4 shows matrix shear strain along the fiber γ_m corresponding to an average strain of about 0.5×10^{-2} . This shear strain in stainless steel / Pb-5Sn was concentrated highly near the fiber end in comparison with almost the same average strain for the composites of W / Ni and W / Al. Yield strain of the matrix was approximately 0.2×10^{-2} so that the greater part of the shear strain would yield, especially in stainless steel / Pb-5Sn. Thus, if the matrix of discontinuous fiber-reinforced metals had low work-hardening and low strength, strain would be concentrated highly in the matrix near the fiber end for transferring a small load to discontinuous fiber, and the matrix would fracture easily or the fiber would pull out easily.

In figure 5, stress distributions of short fibers are shown with plots using the Kelly-Tyson equation and the Piggott equation.¹⁰⁾ These equations are rearrangements for the two-dimensional model; that is, the Kelly-Tyson equation

$$\sigma_f = \frac{8 \tau_m}{\pi} \cdot \frac{x}{d_f} \quad (8)$$

the Piggott equation

Fig.3 Contours of the strain distribution in single short fiber models for average composite strain
 (a) Stainless steel / Pb-5Sn, $\bar{e}_c = 4.1 \times 10^{-3}$
 (b) W / Ni, $\bar{e}_c = 5.2 \times 10^{-3}$

Fig.4 Interfacial shear strain in the matrix of single short fiber models

Fig.5 Tensile stress distribution in a short fiber

$$\sigma_f = \frac{4\sigma_m x}{\pi r_f} + \sigma_m + \frac{4\tau_m}{\beta \pi r_f} \left(1 - \frac{\cosh \beta x}{\cosh \beta (L - l_p)}\right) \coth \beta (L - l_p) \quad (9)$$

$$\beta = \sqrt{\frac{H}{\pi r_f^2 E_f}}, \quad H = \frac{4G_m r_f}{r_m - r_f}$$

where

- σ_f : Stress of fiber
- τ_m : Shear strength of matrix
- σ_m : Strength of matrix
- r_f : Radius of fiber
- r_m : Half width of matrix
- L : Short fiber length
- l_p : Transfer length
- G_m : Shear modulus of matrix
- E_f : Young's modulus of fiber

We made the substitutions of Table 1 in these equations.

In figure 5, stress distribution in the discontinuous fiber in stainless steel / Pb-5Sn was similar to that predicted by the Kelly-Tyson equation or the Piggott equation. But in the short fiber of W / Ni, stress distribution did not follow the Kelly-Tyson equation to as great an extent, because matrix work-hardening would not allow constant interfacial shear stress.

Assuming shear stress is elastic-plastic, the Piggott equation is used for the stress distribution of short fiber. The results seem to almost fit the stress distribution of short fiber in W / Ni. But the non-linearity of the fiber stress is for the work-hardening of the matrix. The elastic effect of interfacial shear stress would be small.

Effects of Discontinuous Fiber Overlapping

In this way, discontinuity in fiber-reinforced metals gives rise to large strain concentrations in the matrix. Thus, interacting discontinuity must be considered. The effects of discontinuous fiber overlapping on the maximums of principal strain and interfacial shear strain in the matrix along the fiber are shown in figure 6 for model (b). When the discontinuous fiber overlapping ratio was 0 or 1 ($l_o/l_f=0$ or 1), the maximum principal strain concentration factor and the maximum interfacial shear strain concentration factor were very large. These strain concentrations rose rapidly as the average composite strain increased. On the other hand, in the case of $l_o/l_f=0.25$ or 0.5, these strain concentration factors were low and rose little as average composite strain increased.

Effects of Fiber Volume Fraction

When discontinuous fiber was flanked by continuous fiber, the strain concentration in the matrix decreased with reducing lateral fiber spacing, that is, with increasing fiber volume fraction. The strain concentration area in the matrix also became narrower on reducing lateral fiber spacing. Figure 7 shows contours of the principal strain in the matrix for model (d). Neighboring continuous fiber almost stopped matrix straining caused by discontinuous fiber. Similarly, interfacial shear strain in the matrix along the discontinuous fiber decreased on reducing lateral fiber spacing. Variations of these concentrations for the space between fibers are shown in figure 8. These effects were very much larger for model (d) than for model (c). Consequently, with a larger fiber volume fraction, the matrix around the discontinuity or interface between fiber and matrix would not fracture easily even at a large average composite strain.

Fig. 6 Growth of maximum values of matrix strain concentration factor $e_m \max / \bar{e}_c$ and interfacial shear strain factor $2\gamma_m \max / \bar{e}_c$ in model (b) (a) Matrix strain (b) Interfacial shear strain

Fig. 7 Contours of the strain distribution in model (d) for average composite strain ($\bar{e}_c = 5 \times 10^{-3}$)

Fig. 8 Variations of maximum strain concentrations and interfacial shear strain concentrations in the matrix for space between fibers.

Fig. 9 Variations of critical fiber length as lateral fiber spacing

But we must take careful note of fiber strain concentration which is generated by the discontinuous fiber end as is mentioned later.

The increasing of fiber volume fraction resulted in changes of fiber strain distribution. The critical fiber length l_c , which was defined as the length necessary to allow the strain in fiber to reach 99% of the average composite strain, decreased on reducing the lateral fiber spacing. Figure 9 shows this decrease in model (c) and (d).

On the other hand, as the fiber volume fraction became high, strain concentration in the fibers which were opposite the discontinuous fiber were generally raised. An example of this strain concentration is shown in figure 7. In this case, the strain concentration factor for average composite strain was about 1.4. This value is similar to that observed by Iremonger and Wood¹¹⁾ for steel fiber-reinforced lead alloy. In elastic fiber-reinforced elastic matrix, Baker and Maclaughlin⁷⁾ calculated the same stress concentration factor by finite element analysis.

These analyses were done in two-dimensional models. In three dimensions, the strain concentration would be smaller than in two dimensions. However, we should consider this strain concentration in order to discuss the fracture of both discontinuous fiber and continuous fiber-reinforced metals.

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